

ISic0306

Large block of uncertain purpose

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 1332

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. cons

Apparatus

Translation (en)

consul (?)

Translation (it)

Commentary

See ISicily 3159 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3159>] for the text on the reverse

Digital identifiers:

TM 491515

EDR 140104

EDCS 21900341

Bibliography

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